

MAPPING THE INTERSECTION OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP AND EMPLOYEE CREATIVITY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the trend of studies on Servant leaders and Employee Creativity. The research method in this study is a quantitative descriptive method and a bibliometric approach. The unit of analysis used is scientific articles, and the research data source comes from scientific publications that review Servant leadership and employee creativity. The research highlights the significance of specific practices that leaders can adopt to promote employee creativity through a Servant leadership approach. Furthermore, it explores the implications of Servant leadership-based interventions across various industry sectors and organization sizes, considering how contextual factors influence the effectiveness of this leadership style. The analysis identifies key countries, institutions, authors, and keywords prevalent in scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity. Implications for future research include identifying specific practices that leaders can implement to enhance employee creativity through a Servant leadership approach. In addition, it can examine the impact of Servant leadership-based interventions across different industry sectors and organization sizes to see how context affects the effectiveness of this approach.

Keywords: Servant leadership, Employee, Creativity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee creativity is the ability to generate new ideas that enable organizations to find business opportunities, solve problems, and achieve organizational goals. To maintain or improve organizational performance in today's highly changing and competitive world, creative behavior from employees is required (Hanaysha et al., 2022).

Organizations may not provide workers with the resources or support they need to develop their innovative ideas, so employees may not have the opportunity to develop their creative abilities through problem-solving activities or intellectual challenges. In addition, employees may not get recognized or rewarded for their creative work, which may lead to them not being motivated to come up with something new (Gonlepa, Dilawar, and Amosun, 2023). Some employees have a prevention focus who tend to avoid risks and choose the safe path, which can hamper their creativity (Sulistiawana, Ekowati, and Putri, 2020).

Leadership plays an important role in the success or failure of an organization. Good leadership can inspire and motivate employees, create a positive work environment, and encourage collaboration and innovation (Zada et al., 2023).

Many phenomena that occur today are related to leadership issues, and only a few people can understand and be sensitive to this leadership issue (Curado and Santos, 2022). Leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance (Nanjundeswaraswamy, 2023).

Leadership style has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. When employees feel unsuitable or unsuitable for someone's leadership style, it can be a factor that makes employees intend to find a new job (Usman, Yanuar, and Marsofiyati, 2022). Servant leadership is one of the leadership styles that support organizational success (Zada et al., 2023). Servant leadership prioritizes service and fulfills employee needs (Su et al., 2020).

Servant leadership is a morally grounded type of leadership where leaders tend to prioritize meeting the needs of employees, customers, and other stakeholders over meeting their own personal needs (Canavesi and Minelli, 2022). Servant leadership creates an environment where everyone's opinions and ideas are valued and encourages people to work together to create solutions to problems (Zada et al., 2023).

Servant leadership can increase employee creativity by creating a confident and collaborative work environment. This type of leadership also encourages employees to develop innovative problem-solving methods. Servant leadership fosters a sense of empowerment among followers and encourages them to share information (knowledge sharing) to improve employee creativity and work role performance in the workplace. The sense of pride and accomplishment that results from their leader's professional activities can inspire them to give back by participating in worthwhile causes (Zada et al., 2023).

By reducing negative conflict and fostering a sense of community, servant leadership emphasizes the well-being of others (Saleem et al., 2020). The focus of Servant leadership is on strengthening relationships with subordinates, so this style engenders a higher level of affective trust in subordinates.

Affective trust results in a stronger emotional connection and a stronger sense of obligation. Servant leadership can improve proactive service performance by increasing their harmonious spirit toward work and customer orientation (Ye, Lyu, and He, 2019). In addition, others' approval of self-dependent self-esteem reinforces the influence of Servant leadership on harmonious work spirit.

The dimensions of servant leader behavior can be identified based on the following seven criteria: 1) Forming concepts, 2) Recovering emotions, 3) Putting followers first, 4) Helping followers grow and succeed, 5) Behaving ethically, 6) Empowering, 7) Creating value for the servan construction society (Chen et al., 2022).

Research on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity has been reviewed by several authors, including The Effect of Servant and Transformational Leadership Styles on Employee Creative Behavior: The Moderating Role of Authentic Leadership. The results show that the creative behavior of employees in organizations is increasing, especially with Servant and transformational leaders armed with authentic leadership traits.

Then the research (Wang et al., 2021) discusses Servant leadership, team reflexivity, coworker support climate, and employee creativity: A multilevel perspective. This research shows that Servant leadership encourages team reflectivity, which in turn increases employee creativity. In addition, this study shows that the climate of peer support moderates the relationship

between Servant leadership and team reflectivity. Finally, Servant leadership and the climate of peer support together influence employee creativity through team reflectivity (the effect of tiered moderation).

However, another study (Kesumadiputra, 2023) discusses the Influence of Servant Leadership and Ethical Leadership on the Creativity of FBE UII Educators: The Role of Organizational Citizenship Behavior as a Mediator. This study shows that Servant leadership has no effect on employee creativity.

Based on the background described, a comprehensive bibliometric study of Servant leaders and Employee Creativity needs to be carried out. This creates a significant knowledge gap in understanding the development trends of Servant Leader topics and Employee Creativity. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to analyze the trend of study on Servant leaders and Employee Creativity.

2. METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a quantitative descriptive method and a bibliometric approach. The unit of analysis used is scientific articles, and the research data source comes from scientific publications that review Servant leadership and employee creativity.

The selection of the Scopus database was made purposively because Scopus has a quality and reputation that has been recognized internationally by universities and research institutions (Fauzy, 2016).

This study uses international publication data on Servant leadership and employee creativity sourced from the Scopus database (www.scopus.com). Data collection through publication searches on Scopus with the search keywords "servant leadership," "employee," and "creativity" with the article title, abstract, and keywords category.

After obtaining the search results, researchers began to explore the data in the Scopus database to examine trends in research development, core journals, researcher productivity and collaboration, publication growth by institution or affiliation, and number of publications by country. Next, we attempted to visualize research progress on Servant leadership and employee creativity using VOSviewer software.

This process involved creating a keyword map by exporting the search results from the Scopus database into CSV format and then inserting the CSV data into the VOSviewer software. This study's data analysis method involved quantitative descriptive and qualitative descriptive approaches.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Trend of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

The trend of scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The trend of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity indexed on Scopus are the most numerous in 2023, with 12 publications.

Number of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Figure 2: Number of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Source: Scopus.com (2024)

Figure 2 shows the top fields of study about Servant leadership and employee creativity, with the following publications: business, management, and accounting (41 publications), psychology (14 publications), and social sciences (7 publications).

Core Journal of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Table 1: Scientific Journal Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Journal Name	Number of publications
Leadership And Organization Development Journal	5
Frontiers In Psychology	4
Current Psychology	3
International Journal Of Contemporary Hospitality Management	3
European Journal Of Work And Organizational Psychology	3

Source: Secondary data processed, 2024

Table 1 shows that the top five journals with the most publications are Leadership and Organization Development Journal, with five publications.

Number of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Figure 3: Number of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Source: Scopus.com (2024)

According to Figure 3, the countries that are productive in publishing research results on Servant leadership and employee creativity are China (18 publications).

Number of Productive Researchers Conducting Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Ten researchers are productive in publishing research results on Servant leadership and employee creativity.

Documents by author

Compare the document counts for up to 15 authors.

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Figure 4: Number of Productive Researchers Conducting Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Source: Scopus.com (2024)

Figure 4 shows that Aboramadan has four publications who are productive researchers who have made scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity.

Number of Scientific Publications on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity by Affiliation/ Institution

Ten affiliates/institutions are productive in disseminating findings from their Servant leadership and employee creativity.

Documents by affiliation

Scopus

Compare the document counts for up to 15 affiliations.

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Figure 5: Affiliates/Institutions that are Productive in Publishing Research Results About Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity

Source: Scopus.com (2024)

Figure 5 explains that the affiliate/institution that is productive in conducting scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity is the University of Science and Technology of China, with four publications.

Author Collaboration Analysis

This study found 174 authors, while the authors had a strong relationship with at least two other authors 9. Visualization of author collaboration in this study can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Visualization of Author's Collaboration

Source: VOSviewer

Viewing author density, as shown by density visualization, is possible with VOSviewer. A larger density of authors suggests extensive study on the subject. The inverse is also true: a low density might present a chance for a fresh investigation. Figure 7 displays the author density in its entirety.

Figure 7: Visualization of Author's Density

Source: VOSviewer

Keyword Analysis

Keyword analysis in this study is from 227 keywords, then selected with the minimum number of keyword occurrences of 5 so that four keywords that have a strong relationship are obtained. The keyword most used by the author is Servant leadership. Visualization of keyword analysis in this study can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Keyword Visualization

Source: VOSviewer

Figure 8 shows that the development map of research publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity indexed in the Scopus database formed 2 clusters.

Cluster 1 is colored red and consists of 2 keywords, including important topics such as employee creativity and Servant leadership. Cluster 2 is green and consists of 2 keywords with important topics of creativity leadership.

VOSviewer can display keyword density as indicated by density visualization. The higher keyword density illustrates that the research topic in that field has been studied a lot. Conversely, if the density is low, it can be an opportunity for new research.

Density visualization explains the density of a term based on the brightness of the visible color. The complete keyword density can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Visualization of Keyword Density

Source: VOSviewer

Figure 9 displays the density of research topics on Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity by keywords. The density of Vosviewer can show which keywords have been covered and which ones have not. In other words, density is used to search for and find novelties in further research related to Servant Leadership and Employee Creativity. In the concept of using density in VOSviewers, the yellow color indicates the most frequently discussed topics; The denser the keywords surrounded by the color yellow, the more research uses that viewpoint as a focus. On the other hand, if the yellow color is not too concentrated in the keyword, then it has not been discussed too much in the research. so that Figure 9 shows that Servant leadership appears most frequently in scientific publications. By understanding the dominant keywords, researchers can explore the most relevant and important topics in this domain.

Discussions

The data presented reflects the increasing number of studies on Servant leadership and employee creativity. A noticeable trend is that there has been a significant growth in the number of studies conducted from year to year, indicating increased attention to Servant leadership and employee creativity. The most dominant or important research areas in the context of Servant leadership and employee creativity are business, management, and accounting. This helps determine the focus of future research and develop more specific interventions to effectively address the issue of employee creativity. The results show an overview of the contributions of various institutions or affiliations to the scientific literature in the domain of Servant leadership and employee creativity. The data presented can help identify influential research centers in this area, allowing stakeholders to evaluate potential collaborations or resources that can be

leveraged to expand knowledge about Servant leadership and employee creativity. Stakeholders can understand the geographical distribution of research on Servant leadership and employee creativity, identifying countries with significant contributions in this area. This information can be used to strengthen cross-country collaboration and address employee creativity issues. VOSviewer visualization results provide insights into the structure of collaboration between authors, identify the most influential or centrally connected authors in the network, and show groups or communities of authors who work together intensively. This information can help researchers understand the dynamics of collaboration in the research field of Servant leadership and employee creativity. In addition, VOSviewer visualizations make it possible to identify research trends and keywords in the scientific literature. By understanding the dominant keywords, researchers can explore the most relevant and important topics in this domain. These visualizations can also help determine future research directions, identify knowledge gaps, and design more in-depth studies to expand the understanding of Servant leadership and employee creativity.

4. CONCLUSION

The number of publications in the global scientific literature about Servant leadership and employee creativity on Scopus reached a peak of 12 in 2023. Business, management, and accounting are the subjects with the most publications, with 41 publications. The journal with the most publications is *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, with five publications. China is a country that is productive in publishing research results on Servant leadership and employee creativity (18 publications). Aboramadan has four publications that are productive researchers who have made scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity. The affiliates/institution that is productive in conducting scientific publications on Servant leadership and employee creativity is the University of Science and Technology of China, with four publications. The authors had a strong relationship with at least two other authors were 9. The keyword most used by the author is Servant leadership. Implications for future research include identifying specific practices that leaders can implement to enhance employee creativity through a Servant leadership approach. In addition, it can examine the impact of Servant leadership-based interventions across different industry sectors and organization sizes to see how context affects the effectiveness of this approach.

Acknowledgments

The authors are very grateful to all those who have helped them with the writing and editing of the article.

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